

The electrical performance of a single-axis sun tracking agrivoltaic system inside a polytunnel greenhouse

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ABSTRACT

This study proposes a novel agrivoltaic tracking system integrated inside rather than above the greenhouse. The innovative single axis 6 kWp photovoltaic (PV) system integrated within a greenhouse is evaluated by analysing the influence of seasonal variations and environmental factors on energy output and performance from May to October. The system achieved a maximum output of 32 kWh per day in June, corresponding with a yield of 5.5 kWh/kWp, comparable to standard outdoor PV systems under similar Mediterranean conditions. However, performance inside the greenhouse was limited by global horizontal irradiance reductions due to greenhouse covers and seasonal dust accumulation. The tracking system demonstrated a 15–20% increase in output compared to a fixed system inside the greenhouse, a reduced effectiveness by structural and environmental limitations inside the greenhouse. Capacity factors were observed to be lower inside the greenhouse (0.18–0.19) compared to outdoor systems (0.20–0.24), reflecting challenges such as partial shading and diffuse irradiance. The performance ratio for the tracking system in July was relatively low (0.65) due to the fact it was inside the greenhouse. This study underscores the potential of agrivoltaic systems inside greenhouses to generate energy effectively while addressing the unique challenges posed by the greenhouse environment.

Introduction

Agrivoltaic systems have emerged as an innovative approach to optimize land use by combining photovoltaic energy production with crop cultivation [1]. These systems utilize the same land area for both solar energy harvesting and agricultural production, addressing the potential competition for land between these two critical sectors. The concept of agrivoltaics was first proposed by Goetzberger and Zastrow in 1981 [2] and has since gained widespread popularity as a means to address concerns over land use change, food security, and biodiversity preservation as well as renewable energy production. Agrivoltaic systems have seen rapid growth, reaching 2.8 GW global capacity in 2020 [3]. The potential of agrivoltaic greenhouses is significant, with studies suggesting they could cover up to 30 % of regional electricity demand, depending on factors such as greenhouse material transmittance and optimal PV cover ratio [4], making agrivoltaic greenhouses an attractive option for farmers, offering dual income streams from crop and energy production. The use of agrivoltaics can also enable the use of additional

technologies to enhance agricultural production, that were perhaps otherwise disregarded due to high energy demands. As such Minanda et al. [5] designed a smart greenhouse to optimise the greenhouse microclimate using integrated photovoltaics to provide a standalone power supply for the greenhouse without impacting agricultural production.

Various PV materials have been studied for greenhouse applications. Semi-transparent PV technologies can better combine crop production and electricity generation. Amongst these, organic photovoltaics (OPVs) are emerging as ideal candidates due to their flexibility, low environmental impact, and tunable absorption spectrum, which can extend to the near-infrared range, potentially reducing heat stress on plants while maintaining visible light transmittance [6,7], which also coincides with the photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) needed by plants. However, OPVs face challenges in outdoor performance and durability [8,9], as well as lower efficiencies and higher costs.

For immediate adoption, more traditional, well proven crystalline silicon PV technologies are more viable solutions [3]. However, some adaptation to standard panel sizes and designs are required when

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Nomenclature

PV	Photovoltaic
kWp	Kilowatt-peak
kWh	Kilowatt-hour
PAR	Photosynthetically Active Radiation
Voc	Open Circuit Voltage
Isc	Short Circuit Current
Vmp	Voltage at Maximum Power
Imp	Current at Maximum Power
RH	Relative Humidity
UV	Ultraviolet Light
OPV	Organic Photovoltaic
Pmax	Maximum Power Output
GHI	Global Horizontal Irradiance (W/m ²)
Pmpp	Power at Maximum Power Point (W)
FF	Fill factor
CF	Capacity Factor
POAI	Plane of Array Irradiance
BF	Bifaciality Factor
PR	Performance Ratio

integrated into greenhouse applications. To increase energy generation, bifacial PV technologies can be used, which have shown an increase of around 10 % in other applications [10]. To achieve semi-transparency with standard opaque silicon cell PV technologies, custom made glass-glass bifacial panels with spaces between cells were used in a greenhouse application, showing promising results in maintaining crop yield while generating electricity in a greenhouse application with cucumber crops [11].

Maximum coverage ratios according to crop type and location are also crucial to achieve optimum growing conditions. A study on an uneven structured greenhouse with PV panels in a checkerboard layout found that a 25 % PV cover ratio reduced energy consumption per kg of tomato by 15.06 % compared to a no-panel scenario [12], showing the potential positive effect of agrivoltaics on crop growth.

Horizontal PV panels can provide some passive shading variation throughout the year, with higher shading in summer and lower in winter. Existing PV installations with N-S horizontal trackers, could also be converted to agrivoltaics by planting crops between panel rows, potentially increasing land efficiency by 28.9–47.2 % [13]. However, variable shading systems, achieved through panel rotation, can optimize both energy and agricultural production by regulating internal radiation levels [14,15]. These systems require careful design to balance sunlight distribution between crops and PV panels. Optimized single-axis tracking schemes for bifacial panels can further enhance agrivoltaic efficiency by customizing panel movement based on crop photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) requirements throughout the day and seasons [16].

Photovoltaic greenhouses have seen rapid expansion in regions such as southern Europe and China, driven by incentive tariffs. However, further research is needed to understand the effect of the different agrivoltaic systems on crops and their potential for electricity production.

This study presents the results from a greenhouse agrivoltaics installation, exploring the potential benefits and challenges of installing PV modules inside rather than outside the greenhouse and the effect of sun tracking compared to static installations. Most greenhouse agrivoltaic systems are integrated above the greenhouse or as part of the greenhouse envelope. The method investigated in this study proposes a novel integration method and analyses its performance. An analysis of the electrical behaviour of the custom agrivoltaic PV panels in a greenhouse agrivoltaic system is presented over a period of 5 months in

one axis East-West sun-tracking mode. A comparison of the system in a fixed horizontal position with the same system in one axis East-West sun-tracking mode is also presented to evaluate the additional gains of the system in tracking mode. In addition, a comparison between panel performance inside and outside the greenhouse is included both in static and sun-tracking modes to evaluate the effect of integrating panels inside rather than on top of the greenhouse. Agricultural results are not presented in this paper.

Methodology

The experimental agrivoltaic system was designed to integrate photovoltaic modules inside an existing polytunnel 140 m² greenhouse in Kfar Qara, Israel. The greenhouse dimensions were 8 m in width and 17.5 m length. The system featured dynamic PV panels in a single-axis tracking system installed 3 m above the ground inside a greenhouse, with soil-grown crops cultivated under the panels (Fig. 1). The tracking system developed by TriSolar InnoWadi Group Ltd. (<https://www.trisolar.net/>) was used in this study, with a sun-tracking control mechanism with a limiting angle $\pm 65^\circ$.

The polyethylene greenhouse cover (Ginegar C460) had the following specifications: thickness of 150 μm , anti-drip properties, light transmittance in PAR of 89 %, UV light transmittance (300–380 nm) of 20 %, diffused light transmittance in PAR of 60 % and thermicity (7–15mic) of 80 %.

The PV modules used were custom-made 105Wp frameless, glass-glass modules (TriSolar LWMH32-105-G1) composed of 44 cells of 105*105 mm in size and with 22.5 % cell efficiency. Spacing between the cells were 20 mm to form an overall panel transparency of 35 %. The module dimensions, cell layout and module specifications are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Agrivoltaic tracking system inside the greenhouse.

Fig. 2. PV module dimensions, cell spacing and module specifications.

57 Modules were connected into 3 strings of 19 cells each and combined to form one input to a grid connected inverter (GoodWe 10 kW). In addition, 2 modules inside the greenhouse and one outside the greenhouse rotated by the same tracker, as well as 2 fixed modules, one inside and one outside the greenhouse, were connected to a PV measurement system (EKO PV Blocks). The arrangement of the PV modules inside and outside the greenhouse is shown in Fig. 3.

The following light and temperature sensors inside and outside the greenhouse were used to monitor ambient irradiance and temperature and incident irradiance on the module, as well as module temperature, in the locations shown in Fig. 4:

Ambient temperature measurements (°C): temperature and humidity sensor -20 to 80 °C, RH: 0-100 %, Shangdong Renke Control Technology Co.Ltd., temperature and humidity transmitter RS-WS-*2-*.

PV module temperature measurements (°C): flat probe temperature sensor -20 to 80 °C, Shangdong Renke Control Technology Co.Ltd., Single temperature transmitter RS-WD-*SMG with flat probe.

Irradiance measurements (W/m²): solar radiation sensor, spectral range: 350 ~ 1100 nm, Shangdong Renke Control Technology Co.Ltd., RS-RA-N01-ALPhotoelectric Total Solar Radiation Sensor.

Fig. 4. Sensor positions inside (a) in the centre of the greenhouse and outside next to the greenhouse (b).

Results

The daily overall 57 PV module 6kWp PV system output and yield per installed kW from May to September can be seen in Fig. 5 (a) and (b) respectively and show a typical seasonal variation over the months due to light availability. Maximum output values around 32kWh per day are achieved in June, which translate to a yield of almost 5.5kWh per kW peak (kWp) installed per day.

However, the global horizontal irradiance (GHI) available inside the greenhouse is reduced due to the greenhouse cover (Fig. 6). A reduction of between 20 % can be seen in May, when the greenhouse cover was new. With ageing of the cover and dust accumulation over the summer period without rain, the average reduction in GHI reaches around 40 %

Fig. 3. PV module arrangement inside and outside the greenhouse.

Fig. 5. Daily PV system output (kWh) for one greenhouse from May to September 2024 (a) and output per kWp installed inside the greenhouse (b).

by the end of July. This is to some extent reflected in the PV output of individual modules inside and outside the greenhouse (Fig. 7), however due to the specific spectral transmittance properties of the greenhouse cover, the reduction in GHI does not fully translate into reduction in output from the PV modules.

Fig. 7 shows the diurnal power output of the 5 individually measured PV modules shown in Fig. 3 above. The modules installed outside clearly had higher outputs compared to the modules installed inside the greenhouse, with peaks in P_{mp} of 97 W for tracking and 88 W in fixed position. The modules installed inside the greenhouse had peaks of 64 W and 66 W in tracking mode and 76 W in fixed position. The typical plateau shape of the tracking modules can be clearly identified for the outside module, thereby maximising the output throughout the day. Inside the greenhouse, the location of the tracking module seems to influence the shape of the output curve. The module on the eastern side of the greenhouse peaks more towards the morning and the one on the western side towards the afternoon. The fixed module is installed on the eastern side of the greenhouse arch and therefore also peaks towards the morning, when it receives more direct light. Interestingly, the output of the fixed module in this instance is higher than the peaks of the tracking modules. This is assumed to be due to differences between module performances from the start.

Fig. 8 shows the diurnal changes in fill factor for the four treatments on the 18.07.2024: 1- fixed horizontal position outside, 2- fixed horizontal position inside the greenhouse, 3- sun-tracking outside the greenhouse, and 4- sun-tracking inside the greenhouse. Fill factor values mainly ranged between 75 and 80 %. For fixed installations, dips in FF can be seen midday. In tracking mode, the FF values were more constant during midday hours and the lower values seen before and after are due to the panels being in a more open position in the earlier hours in the

morning and the later hours in the afternoon/evening (i.e. not directed towards the sun).

Using the data of the individual PV modules on the 18.07.2024, the yield in kWh of the panels was calculated for the day and multiplied by 57 to represent an estimate of a system of the same size as the one installed inside the greenhouse in this study. Fig. 9 shows the estimated yields (kWh/kWp) for the different installation methods. On this specific day, the tracking added 16.1 % and 5.1 % to the output for the panels outside and inside the greenhouse respectively. The reduction in output due to the light reduction from the greenhouse cover was 20.7 % and 12.4 % for the tracking and fixed modules respectively.

Table 1 summarises the generated maximum power per unit area of PV modules on the 18.07.2024 to compare overall performance of the modules in different installation locations. The modules each had a maximum power rating of 105 W as specified by the manufacturer and maximum outdoor GHI was 996 W/m². The estimated system output (kWh) and the yield (kWh/kWp) installed as well as the corresponding capacity factors (CF) are also shown for each installation location.

The capacity factor of a PV system is a measure of its actual energy output over a period of time relative to its potential output if it operated at full rated capacity continuously over the same period [17]. It reflects the efficiency and utilization of the system based on real-world conditions, such as weather, system losses, and operational constraints.

$$\text{Capacity Factor (CF)} = \frac{\text{actual energy output over time}}{\text{rated power} \times \text{time period}} \quad (1)$$

where, actual energy output is the total energy produced by the PV system over the time period (kWh), rated power is the peak power capacity of the PV system under Standard Test Conditions (kW), and time

Fig. 6. Maximum irradiance inside and outside the greenhouse (a) and % in GHI reduction inside the greenhouse compared to outside.

Fig. 7. Pmpp (W) of individual PV modules inside and outside the greenhouse on a clear day 18.07.2024.

period is the duration over which the energy output is measured (24 h in this case).

However, it must be noted that the fact different modules were used

for each installation method means that results could have been affected by initial module differences and not only due to their installation location and method. To counter this effect, the whole PV system installed inside the greenhouse was tested both in sun-tracking and fixed mode. In this way, the same modules were used for both datasets collected. Clear days in May and October were chosen to carry out the experiment. The system was tested on the 9th of May in tracking mode and on the 17th of May in fixed mode. The same test was repeated in October, on the 5th in tracking mode and on the 8th in fixed mode. Results of the system Pmpp in tracking mode vs fixed at tilt angle 0 are shown in Fig. 10. The tracking mode yielded an increase in output of around 15 % in May and 20 % in October. These are close to the typical increases in output of around 20 % due to single axis tracking in outdoor installations [18].

Table 2 shows the system output, yield and capacity factor (CF) for the tracking system in a fixed horizontal position and in tracking mode for one clear day in May and one in October each. Yields, as expected were higher in May, which had longer days and a new greenhouse cover.

Fig. 11 shows that module temperatures were similar inside and outside the greenhouse, which are similar in shape to the power output curves in Fig. 9, indicating that the ambient temperature had less of effect on the module temperatures, and the module temperature diurnal variation was more dependent on the intensity of the incident irradiance on the module. In other words, the tracking modules had higher temperatures throughout a longer period of the day compared to the fixed modules that peaked at times of maximum output and incident irradiance on the panels (Fig. 12)

To evaluate the system performance over a longer period of time, the month of July was selected to calculate yields, CF and performance ratio (PR) of the whole PV tracking system inside the greenhouse. The total output of the 57 PV module, 6kWp tracking system inside the green-

Fig. 8. Fill factor results for PV module outside fixed, inside fixed, outside tracking and inside tracking on the 18.07.2024.

house was 809.1 kWh, equating a yield of 134.9 kWh/kWp installed. The CF for the system over this period of time was 0.18, slightly lower than the one-day analysis in July summarised in Table 1 above. To calculate the PR of the system the following equation was used, as defined in IEC 61724 [17] as:

$$\text{Performance Ratio (PR)} = \frac{Y_f}{Y_r} \quad (2)$$

where:

- Y_f is the system yield defined as the measured energy produced by the PV system in the day (kWh per day) divided by the rated power of the PV system (kW).
- Y_r is the plane-of-array insolation (kWh/m^2) divided by the reference irradiance (1000 W/m^2).

For bifacial modules, the incident irradiance on the rear side and bifaciality factor should also be taken into account. The bifaciality factor is not available for these modules and is estimated as 0.7, a typical value for monocrystalline bifacial PV modules. The total plane of array irradiance (POAI) therefore becomes:

$$\text{Total POAI} = \text{Front side POAI} + \text{Rear-side POAI} * \text{Bifaciality Factor} \quad (3)$$

The total POAI was found to be 209 kWh/m^2 inside the greenhouse in the month of July and the PR was therefore calculated to be 0.65.

Discussion

The performance analysis of a 6 kWp PV system with 57 modules inside and outside a greenhouse, operating from May to October, highlights several key factors influencing energy output, yield, and system efficiency. Seasonal variations significantly impacted PV output, as shown in maximum output values of 32 kWh per day in June, corresponding to 5.5 kWh/kWp. This is typical due to the increased daylight hours in summer and the heightened irradiance, but performance inside the greenhouse was moderated by reductions in global horizontal irradiance (GHI). The performance of tracking PV systems integrated within greenhouses in this study compares to the findings in literature regarding outdoor PV system outputs under similar climatic conditions. Studies on standard non-tracking outdoor PV systems in Israel and similar Mediterranean climates show that typical daily yields range from 5 to 6 kWh per kW installed during peak summer months, depending on factors like orientation and panel technology [19]. The results from this study align closely with these benchmarks, as the

Fig. 9. Calculated output kWh/kWp for a 6kWp 57 modules system on the 18.07.2024 in tracking and horizontal fixed modes, inside and outside the greenhouse.

Table 1

Individual 105 W rated PV modules peak power, daily system output, daily system yield and capacity factors in different installation locations inside and outside the greenhouse on the 18.07.24.

PV module location	Module peak power (W)	Module peak power per m ² (W/m ²)	System daily output (kWh)	Daily yield (kWh/kWp)	Capacity factor (CF)
Outdoor fixed	88	111	29.3	4.9	0.20
Outdoor tracking	97	122	34.0	5.7	0.24
Inside GH fixed	76	96	25.7	4.3	0.18
Inside GH tracking	66	83	27.0	4.5	0.19

greenhouse PV system reached peak yields around 5.5 kWh per kWp installed in June. This suggests that greenhouse agrivoltaic systems, in certain conditions, have the potential to match traditional outdoor

setups in terms of energy generation.

The performance of PV modules inside greenhouses is however inherently influenced by factors unique to the greenhouse environment, such as irradiance reduction from greenhouse covers and localised temperature effects. Previous studies have highlighted similar challenges, with several works reporting significant irradiance attenuation within greenhouses due to cover materials and dust accumulation. For example, Elamri et al. [20] found that seasonal dust buildup can result in

Table 2

System output, yield and capacity factor (CF) for one day in May and one clear day in October.

PV system	Output (kWh)	Yield per kW installed (kWh/kWp)	Capacity factor (CF)
Tracking – May	31.86	5.31	0.22
Fixed – May	28.11	4.69	0.20
Tracking – October	20.32	3.39	0.14
Fixed – October	16.79	2.80	0.12

Fig. 10. System output in tracking mode (red line) vs fixed (blue line) at tilt angle 0. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 11. PV module temperature (grey and black lines) and ambient temperature (green line) outside (a) vs inside greenhouse (b) for a fixed module on 08.10.2024 (black line) and sun tracking module on 05.10.2024 (grey line).

Fig. 12. Temperature difference between PV module temperature and ambient temperature outside (a) and inside the greenhouse (b) for a fixed module (black line) on 08.10.2024 and sun tracking module (grey line) on 05.10.2024.

cumulative GHI reductions within agrivoltaic installations, which aligns with the increase in GHI reduction observed here from 20 % in May to around 40 % by July. This reduction is shown to notably influence PV output in greenhouses, yet, as observed here and highlighted by studies looking at PV greenhouse integration [21] spectral transmittance properties of certain greenhouse covers could partially counteract these effects by selectively allowing high-value wavelengths for PV conversion [22].

The power output comparison between fixed and tracking modules reveals that tracking provides a consistent advantage. The output peaks, however, differ based on module location, with outside tracking modules reaching 97 W, while inside tracking modules achieved lower peaks (64–66 W). Modules inside the greenhouse experienced more variation in diurnal output patterns, influenced by their location relative to sunlight availability inside the greenhouse, with eastern modules peaking in the morning and western modules in the afternoon. The capacity factors (CF) of the modules in the greenhouse remained moderate due to partial

shading and irradiance loss from the greenhouse cover, with CF values ranging from 0.18 to 0.19 for fixed and tracking respectively inside the greenhouse and from 0.20 to 0.24 outdoors for fixed and tracking respectively. Typical capacity factors for fixed systems range from 15 % to 20 %, whereas one-axis tracking can capture more sunlight throughout the day, which generally results in typical CF ranges of 20 % to 30 % [23,24]. The outdoor CF results in this study align with these typical values. However, the results from inside the greenhouse are reduced due to reduced and more diffuse irradiance under the greenhouse cover.

Tests with the entire PV system both in tracking and fixed modes during May and October demonstrated that tracking increases output inside the greenhouse by 15–20 %, closely aligned with the expected 20 % increase for single-axis tracking outdoors. These tests underscore that even within the greenhouse, tracking technology can significantly enhance energy yields, supporting findings from Alshaabani [18] on tracking benefits in outdoor contexts.

The comparative advantage of tracking over fixed modules, both inside and outside the greenhouse, echoes findings from Liu et al. (2020), who reported that single-axis tracking systems in open-field PV installations yield a 20–25 % output increase. The 15–20 % increase observed for the system inside the greenhouse in this study is at the lower end of this range. This more modest increase is likely due to the limited space and spectral filtering effects and diffusion of light passing through the greenhouse cover. This suggests that while tracking remains advantageous, its relative effectiveness in greenhouses is constrained by structural and environmental limitations in greenhouse agrivoltaic systems with cover material that increase diffusion, thereby reducing direct light rays preferable for PV efficiency. Future studies could include adaptation of the cover material to suit both crops and PV module efficiencies. A similar concept was presented by Mamouri et al. [25] that introduced the concept of a spectral-splitting material for the greenhouse to reduce heat inside the greenhouse and to heat a water solar collector. A similar spectral splitting concept could also be used for APV applications [26].

The observed fill factor (FF) behavior aligns with research indicating that tracking systems generally stabilize FF by maintaining optimal light angles throughout the day. For instance, Deceglie et al. [27] reported that PV modules with tracking exhibit less variability in FF due to better alignment with sunlight, even as module positions change. In the greenhouse, the dips in FF observed during midday in fixed installations may result from suboptimal angle configurations, a pattern consistent with findings by Barron-Gafford et al. [28], who noted that fixed installations in shaded or semi-enclosed environments like greenhouses often experience decreased midday efficiency.

Temperature dependencies observed here also reflect trends identified in literature, wherein PV module temperatures closely follow incident irradiance rather than ambient temperature. This is consistent with previous studies by Mirzaei and Mohiabadi [29] that found irradiance, rather than ambient temperature, to be the dominant factor in determining PV module temperature, especially in environments with high light absorption potential, such as agrivoltaic greenhouses. However, the findings in our study also show that tracking modules consistently have higher temperatures due to prolonged sunlight exposure, which could accelerate degradation. This risk is echoed by Khan et al. [30], who suggested thermal management strategies for tracking PV systems to enhance their longevity.

The performance ratio (PR) for the tracking system in the month of July was calculated at 0.65, considering a bifaciality factor of 0.7 for bifacial modules. The total plane-of-array irradiance (POAI) inside the greenhouse in July was estimated at 209 kWh/m² for the period in question. The PR of the system in this study is relatively low compared to typical ranges of 0.80 to 0.90 under standard conditions. In general PR values for tracking systems are higher than for fixed angle systems due to the optimised panel angle relative to the sun, thereby capturing more irradiance throughout the day [31]. However, environmental and location specific factors, such as local climate, irradiance and panel temperature can influence the PR. Hotter climates often see slight PR reductions due to temperature-related losses and high direct irradiance can lead to increased PR [32,33]. In a greenhouse with reduced irradiance with a polyethylene cover that diffuses much of the light, in addition to and higher temperatures inside the greenhouse, the PR values would therefore be expected to be lower. Literature supports the potential of spectral-selective greenhouse covers in mitigating these losses, as they allow wavelengths conducive to PV generation to pass through [34,35].

Overall, these findings contribute to a broader understanding of agrivoltaic system performance especially inside greenhouses and align well with existing literature, emphasizing the role of environmental factors, tracking benefits, and maintenance requirements.

However, to optimise tracking systems for agrivoltaic purposes further, the tracking algorithm should be adapted to provide optimum sunlight sharing between PV and crops. This is an idea proposed by

Imran and Riaz [16], who explored optimal single-axis tracking schemes for agrivoltaics in their study. The single-axis tracking schemes investigated used bifacial panel arrays in East-West and North-South orientations with customized solar tracking schemes by combining modelled temporal variations in shadow patterns on crops and the required photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) by the crop and vary between standard sun tracking and reverse sun tracking, taking into account daily and seasonal variations. Although agricultural aspects were not included in this study, a previous study by the authors that looked at the effect of a static PV system on crop performance in the same greenhouse, in February to June 2022 showed some effect on crop yields due to the PV cover [11]. However, despite this, in their study an LER of 1.34 was calculated for similar PV modules in a static position for the growth period described by Gnyem et al. [11]. In the winter season with lower insolation, the effects could be more significant and therefore a tracking system that is crop responsive, with periods of reverse tracking, is proposed to provide optimum light conditions to the crops grown [36] to enable year round operation. Such a system could also be integrated into AI systems in greenhouses in the future [37].

Another aspect that was not explored in this study was the economic feasibility of this greenhouse agrivoltaic set-up inside the greenhouse, which presents several unique considerations. One of the main advantages of this setup is the ability to reduce costs related to structural elements. By utilizing the existing greenhouse infrastructure to support the photovoltaic (PV) system, the need for additional structures typically required in external agrivoltaic systems is eliminated, leading to direct cost savings. The retrofitting process also benefits from easier access to the interior of the greenhouse, which simplifies installation and maintenance, further reducing costs over time. However, while installation and maintenance costs may be lower, the process still faces certain challenges. Greenhouses come in various shapes and sizes, leading to installation complexities that could increase labor costs. The time required for installation in these varied environments is often longer than that of standard PV systems, which could offset some of the initial savings. Furthermore, the integration of PV modules inside the greenhouse reduces available light for crops, which may affect agricultural productivity and consequently, revenue. The PV modules installed inside the greenhouse also receive less direct sunlight than those in outdoor systems, which leads to a decrease in energy generation, diminishing the overall economic return on the system. For local power consumption, i.e. if the energy generated by the PV system is used to support greenhouse operations, such as powering lights, climate control systems, or irrigation, the system can potentially reduce the reliance on external electricity sources. This can provide significant savings on energy bills and increase the economic viability of the agrivoltaic system. Future work should therefore include a detailed examination of the power economics, comparing costs, energy generation, and local energy use, would provide a clearer picture of the system's overall economic feasibility and help guide future decisions in the development of agrivoltaic systems in greenhouse environments.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study illustrates that tracking agrivoltaic systems within greenhouses can reach energy outputs similar to standard fixed outdoor PV setups under certain conditions. This study however also underscores the challenges and opportunities of integrating PV systems within greenhouses, with irradiance reduction due to greenhouse cover materials emerging as a significant factor affecting PV output. As seen here and supported by findings from Elamri et al. [20] and [21], greenhouse covers cause notable irradiance attenuation, compounded by seasonal dust accumulation. This attenuation is partially offset by spectral transmittance properties, indicating that selecting cover materials with favourable transmittance characteristics could help balance energy production and greenhouse light requirements [34,35].

Tracking technology has proven beneficial both inside and outside

the greenhouse, aligning with performance gains identified by Zhu et al. [38] and Alshaabani [18]. However, as Weselek et al. [39] observed, the advantages of tracking in confined greenhouse environments are somewhat limited, suggesting that while tracking can enhance output, structural constraints should be carefully considered. The stability in fill factor observed for tracking modules here also aligns with Deceglie et al. [27], reinforcing that tracking may support efficiency even in suboptimal lighting environments.

Temperature dependency results highlight irradiance as the primary driver of module temperature, aligning with the work of Mirzaei et al. (2018), and suggesting that managing irradiance impacts on PV modules could be more effective than simply relying on ambient temperature control. Since tracking modules show extended exposure to high irradiance, additional thermal management, as suggested by Khan et al. [30], may help mitigate temperature-induced degradation and extend module lifespan.

These findings collectively support the viability of agrivoltaic systems in greenhouses with proper system design, covering material selection, and regular maintenance to mitigate dust effects. They also indicate that, while tracking systems add measurable value, careful consideration of greenhouse constraints, such as cover type) and module positioning is essential to maximizing output. This study's contributions emphasize agrivoltaic system adaptability, supporting broader deployment potential in agricultural settings where both energy generation and crop production are priorities.

The interaction and light sharing aspects of agrivoltaic systems inside greenhouses should be investigated further and in more detail, to include changes in spectral properties at crop level and light scattering effects due to the greenhouse cover and PV modules. This should include measuring the diffuse and direct parts of the light as well as the spectral irradiance in different spatial locations inside the greenhouse. By understanding the light properties inside greenhouse agrivoltaic set-ups, tracking technologies can be better integrated into greenhouses, by adapting the tracking algorithm to include crop performance to achieve an ultimately more optimum balance between energy and crop production throughout different times of the year and the day, as well as optimising the greenhouse environmental conditions for both plants and PV modules, to optimise crop growth and electricity generation.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT in order to improve readability and language. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

E. Magadley: Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **M. Matar:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **R. Kabha:** Investigation, Data curation. **R. Korabi:** Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **A. Hajyahya:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **A. Abasi:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **H. Barhum:** Investigation, Data curation. **M. Attrash:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **R. Saabne:** Software. **S. Asaly:** Software. **I. Yehia:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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